

Effects of Drought Stress on Qualitative and Quantitative Traits of Mungbean

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Abstract : In order to investigate the effect of drought stress and row spacing on grain yield and associated traits of Mungbean, an experiment was conducted as a factorial in based on randomized complete block design with three replications in Ilam station, Iran during 2008-2009 growing season. This experiment was conducted in four stages on one kind of Mungbean named Gohar. The experimental factors including (80, 110 and 140 mm cumulative evaporation from class A pan) and row spacing (25, 50, and 75 cm) were selected. The results of the experiment showed that the varieties affected by the treatment showed significant differences. The highest total yield was obtained in the condition in which evaporation of water was 80 mm. Of course some traits such as grain yield did not show a significant difference between the conditions in which evaporation of the irrigation water was 80 and 110 mm. the traits under study also showed a significant difference to different row spacing. Row spacing of 50 cm had a higher total yield compared to other row spaces. It was due to the higher number of pods per plant and grain weight. The interaction of drought stress and row spacing showed that in the condition in which the row space is 50 cm and the evaporation of the irrigation water is 80 mm, the highest number of grain is achieved.

Keywords : Mungbean, Drought stress, Row spacing, Grain and its component

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